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INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT AT POULTRY ENTERPRISES IN CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ НА ПТИЦЕВОДЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ АГРАРНОГО РЫНКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Abstract. The increase of economic efficiency of entrepreneurial activity in the sphere of production of poultry farming on the basis of introduction of innovative technologies is considered, the methodology of management of the innovative development of a poultry farm adapted to branch features is developed.

The proposed model for the organization of innovation activity provides for systematic monitoring of the R & D industry market, the implementation of a preliminary assessment of innovation in terms of its scientific and technical viability, efficiency and feasibility, the formation of a database of sectoral innovations, the coordination of the analyzed innovation project with the enterprise strategy and its inclusion in the innovative program of the poultry farm.

Proposals on improving the organizational structure of poultry enterprises are presented.

Аннотация. Рассматривается повышение экономической эффективности предпринимательской деятельности в сфере производства продукции птицеводства на основе внедрения инновационных технологий. Разработана адаптированная к отраслевым особенностям методика управления инновационным развитием птицефабрики.

Предлагаемая модель организации инновационной деятельности предусматривает систематический мониторинг рынка научно-исследовательской отрасли, проведение предварительной оценки инноваций с точки зрения его научно-технической жизнеспособности, эффективности и осуществимости, формирование базы данных отраслевых инноваций, координация анализируемого инновационного проекта с корпоративной стратегией и его включение в инновационную программу птицефабрики.

Представлены предложения по совершенствованию организационной структуры птицеводческих предприятий.

Keywords: innovative development, globalization of agrarian markets, the efficiency of entrepreneurial activity, the introduction of innovative technologies.

Ключевые слова: инновационное развитие, глобализация аграрных рынков, эффективность предпринимательской деятельности, внедрение инновационных технологий.

Poultry farming is one of the most important branches of agriculture, significantly affecting its economy. The highly innovative activity of the poultry product sub-complex is largely due to the

intensive scientific and technological development of the enterprises of material, technical and breeding-breeding support for poultry farming. Factors contributing to the deepening and acceleration of innovative processes in poultry farming, scientists are relatively rapid genetic progress, a good adaptive ability of the bird, as well as a higher level of trans-nationalization of the industry.

Despite the ongoing research work, the national innovation system lags behind its foreign competitors. Institutional problems of poultry development during the transformation of the national economic system make it unlikely for domestic poultry enterprises to pursue an active innovative strategy in the form of technological leadership [1].

The actual state of the organization of innovation activities at the majority of poultry enterprises in the Surdarya region does not allow them to reach a modern level of susceptibility to innovation. The authors assessed the formalization of intra-firm mechanisms of innovative development based on the method of content analysis. The performed analysis shows that Surkhandarya poultry enterprises mainly implement imitation strategies, paying insufficient attention to R & D [2].

The proposed model for the organization of innovation activity provides for systematic monitoring of the R & D industry market, the implementation of a preliminary assessment of innovation in terms of its scientific and technical viability, efficiency and feasibility, the formation of a database of sectoral innovations, the coordination of the analyzed innovation project with the enterprise strategy and its inclusion in the innovative program of the poultry farm.

In conditions of intensive technical and technological development of production, the model of organization of innovation activity is a subsystem of the process of strategic management. [3]

The author's model is oriented toward the analysis of feasibility, the evaluation of efficiency and the selection of innovative projects in order to form an innovative program of the enterprise.

Sectorial features of the innovative development of poultry enterprises require the adaptation of the system of economic analysis of innovations. Figure 1 suggests a system of indicators for assessing the economic efficiency of innovation, modified by incorporating performance indicators that take into account industry characteristics.

At the stage of preliminary assessment of the innovation project and analysis of scientific and technical solvency, commercial, production, organizational, managerial and financial feasibility, NTO staff calculates the integral performance indicators (indicators of the I-st group).

Based on the results of monitoring the industry innovation market, NTO selects and prioritizes innovations based on the I-th group of performance indicators, after which the head of NTO offers the company's management to carry out a comprehensive economic analysis of innovations in the working group.

The working group of experts in the process of evaluating sectoral performance indicators from the III group not only calculates the potential effect of innovation, but also analyzes the need for additional capital costs and changes in technical and technological conditions, and also makes a conclusion on the feasibility and feasibility of including the project in an innovative program (Figure 2).

Then follows the stage of implementation of innovation with the necessary current and retrospective analysis of costs and effects from the introduction of innovation in the enterprise. The natural result of innovation is the change in the position and potential of the poultry enterprise, as well as the adjustment of further goals and priorities for its innovative development.

Figure1. System of indicators of integrated assessment of the effectiveness of innovative projects at a poultry farm

Figure 2. Methods of managing innovation development in poultry enterprises.

A feature of world poultry farming is the pace of innovative development of the industry accelerated in relation to other branches of animal husbandry, which, along with the imitative nature of the innovative strategies of domestic poultry enterprises, makes it necessary to create in the industry developed mechanisms for the transfer of innovations.

The presented methodology for assessing the economic efficiency of sectorial innovations is based on the differentiated complex approach of the model of economic analysis and the author's system of performance indicators for egg production. [4, P. 91-113]

Using the methodology adapted to the specifics of the sub complex will increase the quality and speed of making managerial decisions in the field of innovation and investment.

The authors carried out an assessment of the economic efficiency of applying innovations in egg processing, poultry feeding, introduction of new crosses, and some other industry innovations [5] as tests of the third and fourth stages of the proposed methodology.

Thus, in order to increase the competitiveness and economic efficiency of the poultry product sub complex, it is recommended that the authors create scientific and technical subdivisions at poultry farms to strengthen the institutional framework and accelerate the innovative development of poultry production, and also use a system of indicators and an algorithm for assessing the economic efficiency of innovations at poultry farms to justify management decisions to include projects in the innovation program acceptance.

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